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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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My Journey Through Field Study

Field Study was not just a subject for me. It became a real journey, one that tested my patience, strength, and confidence. From the beginning to the end, I experienced many emotions that helped me understand what it truly means to be a teacher.

On my first day, I felt nervous and unsure of myself. When I entered the classroom, I saw how active and energetic the learners were. Some were standing, some were talking, and others were busy with their own activities. At that moment, I realized that teaching is not easy. It is not just about knowing the lesson; it is also about how you manage the learners and guide them properly.

At first, I had a short briefing with both cooperating teachers. They agreed that I would transfer weekly. I was assigned to Teacher Mary Gee T. Arpon for the first week. She introduced me to her class so the pupils would know who I was inside the classroom. While I introduced myself, the children showed respect by calling me "Teacher Julie Ann," which made me feel welcomed and appreciated. I started to observe my cooperating teacher. I noticed how she used her voice, patience, and strategies to manage the class. I observed that teaching young learners was not easy, but Teacher Mary Gee put forth her full effort to help the students learn. To capture the learners' attention, she used interactive activities to prevent boredom. During this week, I learned how important those skills are.

After a week, I was transferred to another kindergarten class. As in the first week, my cooperating teacher, Teacher Maria Therisa Y. Cuervo, introduced me to the class, and I had a chance to meet them. Observing a different cooperating teacher helped me learn a lot, as they used various strategies to capture learners' interest. During discussions, I noticed how the learners interacted and asked their teacher questions when they did not know the answers. I observed how the teachers managed the learners and got their attention. Teacher Therisa also did her best to manage and guide her learners properly.

As the weeks went by, I continued to learn more in my field study. I helped both my cooperating teachers with their pictorials for the upcoming moving-up ceremony. Assisting these learners was challenging, but I worked to guide them. I observed that if you manage the learners properly, they will follow you. In this way, I learned how to handle these kinds of learners.

Reflecting on my field study experience, I gained valuable lessons about teaching, classroom management, and the importance of creating an inclusive and supportive learning environment. Through this experience, I gained more knowledge and was inspired to keep learning and become a better, more effective teacher someday.